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DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

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Executive Summary

This deliverable report includes an updated version of a Data Management Plan (DMP) for the SEA-Quester project, which addresses the comprehensive management and dissemination of data collected and generated throughout the project's lifespan. The DMP ensures that all data adhere to international standards and best practices, guaranteeing their quality, accessibility, and long-term preservation. It outlines procedures for data storage, backup, and sharing, utilizing a combination of the IOPAN Data Centre and international data repositories and data integrators on the EU and global level.

The project prioritizes free and open access to data, aligning with the principles of open science and the Five Star Open Data Model. This commitment enhances data discoverability and utility for a broad range of users, including researchers, policymakers, and the public. By integrating with major global and European ocean observing systems, the SEA-Quester project ensures that its data contribute to a larger framework of environmental monitoring and research.

The effective implementation of the DMP, under the coordination of a dedicated Data Manager, supports the project's goals of advancing scientific knowledge on polar ecosystems and their role in the global climate system. This strategy not only aids in achieving the project's scientific objectives but also provides a robust foundation for future research and policy development in the context of rapidly changing polar environments.

This document represents the third version of the DMP. Main updates include an added description of the data management infrastructure and the associated centralized cataloguing of metadata describing data collected or processed by the project.

1. Rationale of the project

The accelerated rate of climate change in high-latitude seas is fostering the emergence of novel ecosystems in both coastal regions and the open ocean. SEA-Quester, aligned with the HORIZON-CL6-2023-CLIMATE-01-3 work program, will undertake field surveys, process studies, and model analyses to enhance our comprehension of the causes and consequences of these emerging polar ecosystems. This includes their potential for blue carbon sequestration, implications for marine biodiversity, and their role within the global eco-bio-geo-chemical climate system. SEA-Quester will rigorously analyze blue carbon stocks and their dynamics, establishing a foundation for blue carbon accounting that includes balance sheets not only for carbon sequestration but also for other affected marine ecosystem services such as fisheries production.

SEA-Quester considers all forms of blue carbon in coastal, pelagic, and benthic novel marine ecosystems, encompassing both living and dead matter in the water column and sediments. By employing a mechanistic approach, the project aims to reduce uncertainties in model predictions. A significant outcome of SEA-Quester will be the development of a comprehensive method to quantify the trade-off between harvesting marine biomass and its net contribution to carbon sequestration, termed the Biomass-Sequestration Amplification Factor.

SEA-Quester will ensure effective exploitation of the project results in international scientific assessments of blue carbon potential and by policymakers, specifically targeting Nationally Determined Contribution estimates. The project aims to facilitate dialogue, communication, and dissemination of findings to national and European governmental bodies, European citizens, NGOs, and provide recommendations for optimizing the monitoring of biodiversity and ecosystem services in emerging polar environments.

2. Data management approach

SEA-Quester will implement best practices for free and open science exchange as a core component of its methodology and work plan. All SEA-Quester scientific publications will be made available in open access format under Creative Commons or similar open licenses immediately upon publication. These publications, along with other project outcomes such as model code, satellite algorithms, data analysis protocols, and electronic notebooks, will be disseminated in digital format through a dedicated SEA-Quester community on the Zenodo open science platform (<https://www.sea-quester.eu/>) and/or GitHub for model codes. All published project results will be assigned a persistent identifier by IOPAN, responsible for SEA-Quester's data management, the GeoNetwork facility, or Zenodo. In order to ensure full compliance with open science principles of all Zenodo entries by SEA-Quester partners, our community has been integrated into the EU Open Research Repository.

Furthermore, SEA-Quester emphasizes co-design and co-creation of research through multiple workshops and consultations with various stakeholder groups throughout the project's duration. SEA-Quester adheres to FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable) data principles and the IOC-UNESCO Strategic Plan for Data and Information Management (2023-2029). The project strives to provide timely, free, and unrestricted access to relevant data and associated metadata under the principle "as open as possible, as closed as necessary," with terms and conditions clearly described in this document.

The SEA-Quester DMP was initially published at the project's commencement and continues to be updated as necessary throughout its duration. The DMP guides the consortium through the entire research lifecycle, encompassing data acquisition, organization, curation, storage, preservation, and security, as well as quality assurance, allocation of persistent identifiers, provision of metadata, licensing, and rules and procedures for data sharing. Data management will be performed by existing data centres, adhering to internationally accepted principles and practices, such as those defined by the ICSU World Data System and UNESCO/IOC-IODE.

Data will first be exchanged within the project to facilitate inter-dependent tasks. To this end, a dedicated, secure file sharing infrastructure has been setup using NextCloud (<https://nc.sea-quester.eu/>), with all project members granted read and write access to it. Subsequently, the collected data and information will be made freely and openly available (up to the fifth level of the Five Star Open Data Model) through existing data centres and portals, ensuring validation and re-use by the broader community.

To maximize data discovery and accessibility, metadata for all collected data will be provided in Darwin Core and ISO19115 standards and shared through a dedicated GeoNetwork facility (see details in Section 4). This maximizes interoperability with European and global ocean and marine data management infrastructures, forming the backbone of the European and global ocean observing and data management systems, including those specific to the polar regions: the Sustained Arctic Observing Networks (SAON), the Svalbard Integrated Earth Observing System (SIOS) in the Arctic, and the Southern Ocean Observing System (SOOS) in the Antarctic. Data integrators will include, but are not limited to: SeaDataNet, EMODnet, and the Ocean Biogeographic Information System (OBIS), which implement state-of-the-art cloud technology and offer accompanying software, products, and reports for data viewing and further analysis. Long-term preservation of data will be secured through dedicated and trusted data centres and repositories, with data mirroring across different infrastructures where possible. Depending on the type of collected data, these will be permanently archived in national and international repositories (e.g., National Oceanographic Data Centres, PANGAEA, ICES). The costs of data curation, preservation, and personnel related to research data management have been included in the proposed project budget (WP7-8), with additional resources provided by the public repositories.

Consortium partners DTU and IOPAN constitute the body designated to coordinate the data management activities. SEA-QUESTER partners' IT Departments provide necessary expertise and capacity to assure proper data management.

A designated Data Manager, Marcin Wichorowski (a data expert appointed by IOPAN), has been incorporated into the project team. The Data Manager's main tasks are to coordinate efforts engaged in data acquisition and to provide support with tools for data transformation and upload. He is responsible for implementation of this Data

Management Plan and coordination of data evaluation and overview of data management practices within the data life cycle frame. In addition, Karolina Gorn (IOPAN) also provides support with metadata and data submission process to all project partners, including through online tutorials and help desks.

3. Data identification and description

3.1 Data types and standards

Ship-based measurements, fixed-point time-series observations, and visual (scuba diving) surveys will be the main means of collecting in situ ocean data for the project. SEA-QUESTER will collect data on parameters spanning all ocean disciplines: physical, chemical, biological, and geological, ranging from coastal to open ocean, and from surface to deep ocean. The majority of measured parameters are considered sub-variables of Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) as defined by the Global Ocean Observing System, for which there are robust guidelines, best practices, or standard operating procedures already in place on how to obtain comparable, high-quality measurements. The project will ensure the use of the relevant EOVS Specification Sheets (www.gooscean.org/eov), which will be updated as part of the EU BioEcoOcean project with which SEA-Quester strongly liaises. Data and model-derived products, such as indices or indicators, will also be generated according to requirements co-created via stakeholder consultation workshops.

Project members will be informed about and encouraged to comply with any agreed quality control procedures and other community best practices published in the Ocean Best Practices System (OBPS) repository (www.oceanbestpractices.org/), an activity coordinated by IOC-UNESCO. In general, OGC (Open Geospatial Consortium), ISO, NetCDF, and the International Oceanographic Data and Information Exchange (IODE) standards will be used. For ship-based hydrographic data (such as temperature, salinity, nutrients and carbonate system parameters), we will refer to standards established by the Global Ocean Ship-Based Hydrographic Investigations Program (GO-SHIP; www.go-ship.org/HydroMan.html) and the International Ocean Carbon Coordination Project (IOCCP; www.ioccp.org/documents/standards-and-methods), as well as OBIS and GBIF for majority of biology and ecosystem measurements. Fisheries data from acoustic surveys, as well as fish and plankton data collection will be guided by the ICES metadata standards and sampling protocols.

Level 0 data (raw data) will be acquired and stored for further processing using variety formats. Data collected in situ depends on design of the measuring equipment's firmware. In most cases, measuring equipment either is supported by software tools provided by the vendor for data pre-processing, or can return non-proprietary file types with structured data. Samples collected in situ have to be processed together with associated metadata and deliver text files (.csv), numerical files (NetCDF .nc format) and multimedia material (photos and video sequences). Multimedia objects typically deliver large binary files.

SEA-QUESTER also generates model outputs which will form the basis for scientific publications. Outputs will be stored either as text files or numerical files. All model code developed during the project's lifetime, together with supporting documentation, will be made publicly available on GitHub (web-based hosting service for version control using Git) or similar open access repositories to foster further exploitation and innovation. If possible, all code shared through GitHub should also be accessible through the SEA-Quester Zenodo community.

Variables or parameters measured, or derived from raw data, by organizations involved in SEA-QUESTER are grouped according to BODC P03 vocabulary, wherever applicable. Table 1 provides an overview of datasets which will be assembled during the project, mostly delivered as milestones. A full catalogue with a detailed list of parameters under each group will be provided when more complete metadata records become available on GeoNetwork, and after the publication of consecutive milestones related to data compilations and data products. While the majority of sampling campaigns were completed in 2024-2025, further fieldwork is planned in 2026 and likely also in 2027.

Table 1: Initial overview of datasets to be produced in SEA-QUESTER.

WP	Lead partner	Description of data
WP1	IOPAN	Optical, phytoplankton biomass and diversity in situ measurements
WP1-2; M1.1	UBREMEN	Compilation of zooplankton biomass data from literature and unpublished data
WP1, WP5; M1.4	UBREMEN	Data set on benthic foraminiferal, invertebrate and microbial productivity and diversity in surface sediments
WP1-5; M2.1	AWI	Data set of size-specific settling velocities as a function of aggregate composition and type
WP1-2; M2.2	AWI	Data set of carbon flux and organic aggregate type from periods with contrasting plankton communities
WP2-5; M3.1	IMPERIAL	Data set on respiration, faecal pellet production and deadfalls to describe passive and active fluxes of the biological carbon pump
WP1-5; M3.2	IMPERIAL	data set on seasonal lipid composition in zooplankton in the Arctic
WP4-6; M4.2	AU	Compilation of relevant literature sources concerning carbon content in sediments in different regions
WP4-6; M5.3	AU	Quantification and mapping of the amount of sedimentary blue carbon potential for different environments and different scenarios
WP3-5; M5.4	AU	Quantification of the biomass sequestration amplification factor
WP2, WP6; M6.2	HEREON	Modelling data required for fishing impact
WP7-8; M8.1	GRIDA	GIS layers based on other WP outcomes
		plankton traits data (size, feeding mode, diet, overwintering strategy, vertical migration)

The storage allocated for the volume of data acquired during field expeditions and collected archive data used for this research is up to 30TB including numerical model outputs, satellite images, and multimedia files. This storage will be extended according to growing demands of project development teams and optimized to comply with technological advances. Through public repositories, Data will be preserved and availability for users in perpetuity. Biological samples will be preserved at least 5 years after publication of data and termination of the project.

3.2 Re-use of existing data

A current list with examples of existing data of which SEA-QUESTER has already used or anticipates to use is provided in Table 2. To complete the work and meet project goals, an extensive review of archive data and data available in repositories, especially dedicated for Arctic data has been conducted providing the basis for several

milestone reports associated with such data assembly or synthesis. More details on these compilations, especially when published, will be incorporated into the future revisions of the DMP. For operational use data will be replicated locally, if necessary.

Table 2: Existing data and products used or to be used in SEA-QUESTER.

Data set	Focus	Coverage		Responsible
		Time	Area	
KRILLBASE	Zooplankton, krill and salps	1920-2020	Circumpolar Antarctic	IMPERIAL
Hausgarten	Hydrology, ice-distribution, plankton, export flux	2000-2020	Arctic, Fram Strait	AWI
CDOM-HEAT	Optical properties: chl- α , dissolved organic matter fluorescence, coloured dissolved organic matter.	2013-2016	West Svalbard, Fram Strait	IOPAN DTU
AREX-HPLC	HPLC phytoplankton pigments	2000-2005, 2014-2022	East Greenland, West Svalbard	IOPAN
AREX - C14	C ¹⁴ in situ primary production	1994-2019 summer	Horsund, Kongsfjorden	IOPAN
Kongsfjorden seaweed	Biomass & biodiversity	1998, 2014, 21	Kongsfjorden Svalbard	AWI
Kongsfjorden physical	Irradiance, temperature, salinity, carbonate system, chl-a	2012-present	Kongsfjorden Svalbard	AWI
Carbon and trace metals	alkalinity, dissolved inorganic carbon and trace metals	2020-2023 summer	Kongsfjorden, East and West Greenland	HEREON
Ra Greenland	Ra measurements	2021, 2022	East and West Greenland	HEREON
Biogeochemistry	Carbonate chemistry	2016, 2019 2021-2023	West Greenland	GINR
Mooring	temperature (T), salinity (S), Turbidity, chlorophyll-a (Chl-a), pCO ₂	2022-present	West Greenland	GINR
Mooring	Acoustics	2020- present	East and West Greenland	GINR
Plankton	Seasonal data on Chl-a, flow cytometry, DNA and zpl	2016-2023	East and West Greenland	GINR
Zooplankton	Seasonal zooplankton	2005-present	East and West Greenland	GINR
Aarhus University	Sedimentary records: T, S, sea ice, O ₂ , productivity, carbon turnover	Holocene, last 14,000 y	East and West Greenland, Newfoundland, Iceland	AU
Greenland	dissolved organic carbon in open ocean	2021	West Greenland	IOPAN
Contrast	Water & sediment chemistry	2015-2016	Kongsfjorden and Hornsund (Svalbard)	IOPAN
Polygon	CO ₂ system (surface + water)	2019-2021	Fram Strait	IOPAN
Spitsbergen	Water and meltwater chemistry	2020-2022	Svalbard	IOPAN
ARICE - NoTAC	Microbial, production, nitrate uptake, degradation dissolved organic matter	2021	Fram Strait	DTU
HELCOM Monitoring	Seasonal data on pelagic	2010-20	Bothnian Sea	IOW

Project has been and continues to generate data. List of data acquired and still planned to be acquired during project works is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Types of data intended to be generated in SEA-QUESTER.

Partner	Types of Data Generated
IOPAN	Optical, phytoplankton biomass and diversity in situ measurements
UBREMEN	Compilation of zooplankton biomass data from literature and unpublished data
UBREMEN	Data set on benthic foraminiferal, invertebrate and microbial productivity and diversity in surface sediments
AWI	Data set of size-specific settling velocities as a function of aggregate composition and type
AWI	Data set of carbon flux and organic aggregate type from periods with contrasting plankton communities
IMPERIAL	Data set on respiration, faecal pellet production and deadfalls to describe passive and active fluxes of the biological carbon pump
IMPERIAL	Data set on seasonal lipid composition in zooplankton in the Arctic
AU	Compilation of relevant literature sources concerning carbon content in sediments in different regions
AU	Quantification and mapping of the amount of sedimentary blue carbon potential for different environments and different scenarios
AU	Quantification of the biomass sequestration amplification factor
HEREON	Modelling data required for fishing impact
GRIDA	GIS layers based on other WP outcomes Plankton traits data (size, feeding mode, diet, overwintering strategy, vertical migration)

4. Data organization and exchange

Data will be extracted from raw instrument and observational files and stored in a relational database environment to support further processing, including quality control (QC), harmonisation, and metadata discovery. Raw and intermediate data remain under the responsibility of the data originators, who ensure their integrity, versioning, and traceability throughout the data lifecycle. Data originators are also responsible for enriching datasets with comprehensive metadata and applying discipline-specific quality assurance procedures prior to internal and external exchange.

Metadata describing datasets, data products, and services are managed centrally using a dedicated GeoNetwork metadata management system. GeoNetwork acts as the authoritative catalogue for the project, supporting the creation, validation, publication, and harvesting of metadata records compliant with international standards such as ISO 19115/19139 and Darwin Core. The system enables structured metadata entry, controlled vocabularies, multilingual descriptions, and linkage between datasets, derived products, services, and related publications through persistent identifiers. GeoNetwork provides standard interfaces (e.g. OGC CSW, OAI-PMH) to ensure interoperability with European and global marine data infrastructures and to facilitate automated metadata harvesting by external catalogues and aggregators.

All project partners are requested to submit standardized metadata records for all collected data to the IOPAN GeoNetwork facility (<https://geonetwork.iopan.pl/>). Assistance with metadata record submission is provided by IOPAN data management team. Initial records should include a minimum set of metadata as agreed by the consortium, and be gradually expanded into full records as data becomes processed and ultimately disseminated. A dedicated catalogue for SEA-Quester is being maintained and can be used to publically view all currently published records associated with project data (<https://tinyurl.com/sea-quester-geonetwork>). All project partners can maintain draft records until they are ready to be published. Records can be updated at any time, even after their publication.

Figure 1: First publicly available metadata records of data collected and/or published by SEA-Quester project partners. Screenshot from IOPAN GeoNetwork facility (January 2026).

Quality-controlled datasets are shared among project partners involved in the development of higher-level data products. These products may be generated at different levels of complexity, ranging from harmonised observational datasets to derived indicators, gridded products, and model outputs, in order to maximise interoperability and reusability by external users. Data exchange within the consortium is supported by standardised formats and agreed conventions, ensuring consistency across work packages and disciplines.

All published datasets and data products are made openly accessible to external users through recognised data centres and repositories, with their discovery enabled via the GeoNetwork catalogue. Access conditions, licences, provenance information, and links to related resources are clearly described in the metadata. In line with the FAIR data principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016), published data are findable through persistent identifiers and searchable metadata, accessible via standard protocols, interoperable through the use of common formats and vocabularies, and reusable through clear licensing, rich metadata, and documented quality control procedures. These provisions apply both during the project lifetime and after its completion, ensuring long-term usability and impact of SEA-Quester data outputs.

A dedicated and interactive online tutorial has been created to assist all project partners in complying with the agreed process of data organization and exchange, with focus on how to create metadata records on GeoNetwork. The tutorial, updated as needed, is accessible from here: <https://tinyurl.com/sea-quester-dmp-tutorial>. In-person help desks to support the implementation of the DMP were also organized during the 2025 Annual Project Meeting, with similar plans for the 2026 and 2027 meetings.

Figure 2: Screenshot of the interactive menu from the GeoNetwork tutorial available to the SEA-Quester consortium

5. Data storage and backup

Data storage is provided by the IOPAN Data Centre. Infrastructure of the Centre is HA enabled, and electronic equipment is powered by uninterruptible power sources. The data is replicated to PLGRID – an external private cloud developed for scientific purposes on national level in Poland. Local archive is supported by Barracuda Tape Library certified for two hours fireproof. This tape library is part of the distributed file system providing continuous backup activity.

To enhance resilience and protect against data loss, project data are replicated to PLGRID, a national scientific private cloud infrastructure in Poland, providing geographically distributed storage and additional computational capacity. This replication supports both operational data processing and disaster recovery scenarios. Local long-term archiving is supported by a Barracuda Tape Library, certified for two-hour fire resistance, which forms part of a distributed file system enabling continuous and automated backup procedures. This solution ensures regular snapshotting, versioning, and recovery of datasets at different stages of processing.

In addition to institutional and national infrastructures, selected datasets and final data products may be deposited in trusted external data repositories, such as Zenodo and PANGAEA, depending on data type, maturity, and community relevance. These repositories provide persistent identifiers (DOIs), long-term preservation guarantees, and wide international visibility. Depositing data in such repositories acts as an additional safeguard, complementing institutional storage and backup systems, and supports long-term access beyond the project lifetime.

The combined use of institutional, national, and international data centres ensures a robust, multi-layered data storage and backup strategy, aligned with FAIR principles and best practices for research data preservation.

6. Data sharing, standards & metadata

To enhance FAIRness of the data and data products of SEA-QUESTER, all data generated by project will be associated with metadata. The most popular standards of metadata are these derived from ISO19115 and ISO 19139 including INSPIRE and SeaDataNet. All necessary metadata will be discovered by ETL tools and associated with data. To exchange data with external users (including automated systems) metadata will be attached to data requested by users on-the-fly according to demanded format.

The formats of data provided by system will be developed according to identified user's needs (both internal and external), initially delivered as NetCDF, ODV, and CSV (text) files.

To maximize data discovery and access using innovative and effective open science practices, metadata for all collected data will be provided in Darwin Core and ISO19115 standards. This metadata will be shared through a dedicated GeoNetwork facility to ensure interoperability with European and global ocean and marine data management infrastructures (see details in Section 4).

Agreed-upon quality control procedures from the Ocean Best Practices System repository will be employed to curate the data, using flags and possible corrections. Long-term preservation of data will be secured through operations of dedicated and trusted data centres and repositories, with data mirrored across different infrastructures where possible. Depending on the type of collected data, they will be permanently archived in national and international repositories such as National Oceanographic Data Centres, PANGAEA, and ICES.

The costs of data curation, preservation, and personnel related to research data management have been included in the proposed project budget (WP7-8).

7. Data restrictions

Each organization is responsible for ensuring that their collection, processing and sharing of personal data and / or special categories of personal data comply with Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 (the General Data Protection Regulation, or GDPR) and other applicant regulation on personal data. The Parties will therefore ensure the legal foundation for the data and ensure the contractual basis and take required security measures in accordance with GDPR before sharing any personal data and / or special categories of personal data. The SEA-Quester Partners agree that any sharing of data to the widest extent possible will be in completely anonymized form not containing any personal identifiable data and therefore not subject to GDPR. If it is not possible for the Parties to share personal data in completely anonymized form, the Parties agree to use the EU provided templates for transfer of personal data and for processing of personal data cf. decision 2004/915/EC, decision 2001/497/EC and decision 2010/87/EU.

Each organization acts as data controller for the procession of these personal data, with reference to each Party's privacy policy and GDPR. The Consortium Agreement regulates the ownership and access to key knowledge and

intellectual property, and developed issues with rights and confidentiality. DTU, as project manager, will advise the consortium on any issues.

Data will conform with Open Access policy and will be published as soon as quality assurance procedures are applied. Where possible, SEA-QUESTER will promote the high standard of openness by deploying the Five Star Open Data Model. To score the maximum five stars, data must (1) be available on the Web under an open license, (2) be in the form of structured data, (3) be in a non-proprietary file format, (4) use URIs as its identifiers, (5) include links to other data sources.

SEA-QUESTER is primarily generating and analysing environmental data. These data are neither sensitive/personal nor restricted data.

8. Data publishing & licensing

Data generated within the project will be published in scientific, peer-reviewed journals with required open accessibility of underlying data. Additionally, all data will be open to users on Creative Commons license after publication with no restriction.

SEA-QUESTER is strongly committed to free and open data exchange and interoperability. First, data will immediately be exchanged within the project, through the NextCloud file sharing cloud space or otherwise, to enable performance of interdependent tasks. Second, the collected data and information will be made freely and openly available through portals operating both on the European platforms (e.g. EMODnet, PANGAEA, SIOS, ICES) or other, thus ensuring they are validated and available for re-use by the wider scientific community. All data can initially be deposited on IOPAN Data Centre and replicated to other repositories. Data from hydrographic cruises conducted along regular GO-SHIP lines are recommended to be deposited in CCHDO (<https://cchdo.ucsd.edu/>). Surface ocean carbon data, if of sufficient quality, is typically submitted either to NOAA NCEI OCADS (<https://www.ncei.noaa.gov>) or to SOCAT (<https://www.socat.info/>) with which it is interoperable and which now supports automatic data and metadata submissions. A majority of biological data on phytoplankton, zooplankton, biota composition, and rate measurements, as well as paleoceanographic data, will be deposited to OBIS, GBIF, EMODnet or to PANGAEA. Data on fluxes and suspended particulate material from the Arctic Ocean is typically deposited in the NIRD Research Data Archive (<https://archive.norstore.no/>), available also through the Svalbard Integrated Arctic Earth Observing System (SIOS; <https://sios-svalbard.org/>). The National Centre for Biotechnology Information (NCBI; <https://submit.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>) is most suited to accepting omics and proteomics data types. Other dissemination platforms might be used to provide free, open and FAIR access to other types of data, including fish surveys, and socio-economic data.

As part of the SEQ-QUESTER project, the publication of generic project metadata will be carried out through the GeoNetwork system, which enables the cataloguing, discovery, and dissemination of information about data resources in accordance with international standards such as ISO 19115, Dublin Core, and INSPIRE. Making metadata available via this system ensures transparency, facilitates resource discovery, and supports the implementation of the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), which are the foundation of modern scientific data management.

The GeoNetwork system for the SEQ-QUESTER project is maintained and provided by the Institute of Oceanology of the Polish Academy of Sciences (IO PAN) and is accessible at <https://geonetwork.iopan.pl>. This service operates as an open catalogue platform, ensuring metadata interoperability with other European and global information systems by supporting protocols such as OGC CSW (Catalogue Service for the Web) and OAI-PMH. This enables the integration of project data descriptions with external repositories and research infrastructures such as EOSC, SeaDataNet, or GEOSS.

Metadata publication in GeoNetwork will include descriptions of datasets generated or used within the project, indicating their sources, formats, access rights, and conditions for reuse. The system also supports metadata versioning and updating, which is essential in the context of the dynamic nature of research projects. As a result, users — including researchers, decision-makers, and representatives of civil society — will have access to reliable and up-to-date information about the SEQ-QUESTER project's data resources.

To maximize the possibility of data discovery and access to data and information using innovative and effective open science practices, metadata for all collected data will be provided in appropriate standards to key Pan-European and global ocean and marine data management infrastructures. The domain of data integrators includes but is not limited to SeaDataNet (<https://www.seadatanet.org/>), EMODnet (<http://www.emodnet.eu/>) and Ocean Biogeographic Information System (OBIS; <http://iobis.org/>), the organizations which implement state-of-the-art cloud technology, and offer the use of accompanying software, products and reports to view and further analyse the data alongside other information found across the associated data repositories. Following the recommendations of the GEO Marine Biodiversity Observing Network (MBON), SEA-QUESTER will specifically engage with the European node of OBIS to exploit the possibility of directly submitting or linking co-located biodiversity and environmental data and consistent metadata prepared according to one of the recommended standards.

9. Data archiving

Management of data will be performed by existing data centres in adherence to international accepted principles and practices, e.g. as defined by the ICSU World Data System (www.icsuwcs.org). Agreed quality assurance and quality control (QA&QC) procedures will be used to curate data, using flags and possible corrections. Long-term preservation of data through the Global Earth Observation System of Systems common infrastructure is ensured through a reference registry and mirroring data in different data infrastructures. Depending on the type of collected data, they can be permanently archived in national and international databases (e.g. PANGAEA, NCEI, ICES). For operational purposes, data collected and generated by the project can initially be hosted at IOPAN Data Centre and replicated to selected infrastructures. Costs of data archiving have been included in the project budget.

Data remain on the same level of accessibility after project completion and termination. To assure a long-term, stable state of data accessibility, SEA-Quester will use resources of IOPAN Data Centre and replicate data with other data systems, e.g. PANGAEA and SeaDataNet.

This far horizon strategy will assure long-term data accessibility, resilient for possible fault occurrences affecting one of the data systems, where data are stored. This accessibility is highly important for future environmental studies since environmental data, in particular data acquired within field campaigns, has value that is hard to overestimate.

10. Conclusions

This deliverable report provides an updated version of the SEA-Quester DMP which details the selected approach to data management to make the practices fully in line with the Horizon Europe programme requirements for delivering open science, and reflects feedback both from the consortium members and the EC after the first 24 months of the project duration. The project has begun to generate first datasets based on newly assembled historical data and newly collected data using field surveys, process studies, and model analyses to enhance our comprehension of the polar ecosystem dynamics and their potential for carbon sequestration. Along with a wealth of other datasets originating from the 2024-2026 field campaigns, the project also aims to deliver novel data synthesis products or policy-relevant indices such as the Biomass-Sequestration Amplification Factor which quantifies the trade-offs between harvesting marine biomass and carbon sequestration potential.

The report provides updated information on best practices in data management to the project consortium, in particular with respect to sharing timely and standardized metadata, ensuring that all scientific outputs, including publications, model codes, and data, are openly accessible through platforms like Zenodo and GitHub. Implementation of the DMP will ensure that the project adheres to FAIR principles, thus making the produced data findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable. A comprehensive DMP guides the project's data lifecycle, covering acquisition, storage, quality assurance, and long-term preservation. The DMP will continue to be regularly updated and shared with stakeholders, including policymakers and the scientific community, to support international assessments and fact-based policy-making.

References

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